

A D-Phenylalanine-Benzoxazole Derivative Reveals the Role of the Essential Enzyme Rv3603c in the Pantothenate Biosynthetic Pathway of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

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ABSTRACT: New drugs and new targets are urgently needed to treat tuberculosis. We discovered the D-phenylalanine-benzoxazole **Q112** displays potent antibacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) in multiple media and in macrophage infections. Metabolomic profiling indicates that **Q112** has a unique mechanism of action. **Q112** perturbs the essential pantothenate/CoA biosynthetic pathway, depleting pantoate while increasing ketopantoate, as would be expected if ketopantoate reductase (KPR) were inhibited. We searched for alternative KPRs since the enzyme annotated as PanE KPR is not essential in *Mtb*. The ketol-acid reductoisomerase IlvC catalyzes the KPR reaction in the close *Mtb* relative *Corynebacterium glutamicum*, but *Mtb* IlvC does not display KPR activity. We identified the essential protein Rv3603c as an ortholog of PanG KPR, and demonstrated that purified recombinant Rv3603c has KPR activity. **Q112** inhibits Rv3603c, explaining the metabolomic changes. Surprisingly, pantothenate does not rescue **Q112**-treated bacteria, indicating that **Q112** has an additional target(s). **Q112**-resistant strains contain loss-of-function mutations in the twin arginine translocase TatABC, further underscoring **Q112**'s unique mechanism of action. Loss of TatABC causes a severe fitness deficit attributed to changes in nutrient uptake, suggesting that **Q112** resistance may derive from a decrease in uptake.

Keywords: PanG, coenzyme A, ketopantoate reductase, 2-dehydropanoate 2-reductase, IlvC, TatABC

Tuberculosis (TB) remains among the most pernicious human diseases. Approximately 1.4 million deaths were associated with tuberculosis in 2019, and 10 million new cases were reported worldwide ¹. The etiological agent *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) is especially difficult to eradicate because the bacteria inhabit diverse environments that vary in pH, nutrient and oxygen availability ². *Mtb* can be free living or intracellular *in vivo*, and can also be replicating or quiescent. Different metabolic pathways are vulnerable in each environment/growth state and drugs penetrate these environments to varying extents ³. Therefore several different antibiotics are required to eliminate *Mtb* infections, as well as to guard against the development of resistance ⁴. The treatment of even drug susceptible *Mtb* is challenging- standard treatment requires a four antibiotic regimen that spans six months ¹. The complicated, long duration treatments engender poor patient compliance, creating an environment ripe for the development of antibiotic resistance. Approximately 0.5 million cases resistant to the frontline drug rifampicin were reported in 2019, 78% of which were multi-drug resistant. These infections require treatment with more toxic second line drugs, often with durations of 2 years or more. Better treatment regimens are desired for drug susceptible tuberculosis, and new antibiotics are urgently needed to treat drug resistant infections.

While drug discovery has been dominated by a “one drug-one target” paradigm, there is a growing appreciation for the advantages of drugs that engage multiple targets ^{5,6}. Indeed, the efficacy of many of the most widely used drugs such as aspirin and metformin has been attributed to pleiotropic effects on multiple targets. While the same effects can potentially be achieved with the administration of drug cocktails, multi-target drugs have the advantages of ease of administration, lack of drug-drug interactions, and more straightforward clinical development. Multi-targeting is particularly appealing for the treatment of tuberculosis, where polypharmacology can potentially address the variation in target vulnerability with environment/growth state as well as discourage the emergence of resistance ⁷⁻¹⁰. Several laboratories are actively pursuing a multi-targeting strategy in TB drug development ¹¹⁻¹⁵, and the potential of this approach is demonstrated by the clinical development of SQ109 ².

Our laboratories and others have been developing inhibitors of *Mtb* inosine monophosphate dehydrogenase 2 (IMPDH2) as potential antitubercular agents ¹⁶⁻²¹. A benzoxazole scaffold, which we named **Q**, has yielded *Mtb*IMPDH2 inhibitors with antibacterial activity comparable to that of the frontline drugs

isoniazid and rifampicin^{17, 22}. However, while the antibacterial activity of some **Q** compounds clearly derives from inhibition of *Mtb*IMPDH2 as designed, the mechanism of action of others is uncertain¹⁷.

Here we report the D-phenylalanine-benzoxazole **Q112**, a weak inhibitor of *Mtb*IMPDH2 that nonetheless displays potent antibacterial activity. **Q112** does not elicit the characteristic changes in nucleotide pools observed when *Mtb*IMPDH2 is inhibited. Instead, **Q112** perturbs the essential pantothenate/CoA biosynthetic pathway, depleting pantoate while increasing ketopantoate, as would be expected if ketopantoate reductase was inhibited. We find that Rv3603c is a previously unrecognized PanG ketopantoate reductase that is sensitive to **Q112**. Surprisingly, pantothenate does not rescue **Q112**-treated bacteria, suggesting that **Q112** has an additional target(s). **Q112**-resistance bacteria carry loss-of-function mutations in the TatABC translocase, the first example of resistance associated with this protein complex, and further underscores the unique mechanism of **Q112**. Loss of TatABC is likely to have widespread effects on permeability, suggesting that **Q112**-resistance may result from decreased uptake.

RESULTS

Q112 Has Potent and Specific Antimycobacterial Activity. **Q112** emerged from our *Mtb*IMPDH2 inhibitor program (Figure 1A)¹⁷, displaying potent antibacterial activity against freely replicating *Mtb* H37Rv (1 week MIC = 0.78-1.5 μ M, Table 1). The enantiomer, **Q111**, is less active by a factor of approximately 25 (MIC = 25-37 μ M; Table 2). Since antibacterial activity can vary dramatically in different growth conditions, we evaluated the effect of **Q112** on bacteria cultured on different carbon sources or in the presence of nitrite, which mimics conditions in the phagosome (Table 1). Antibacterial activity varied by less than a factor of 2 under these conditions, indicating that **Q112** may be effective in many of the microenvironments occupied by the bacteria *in vivo*. In addition, **Q112** is more effective in the absence of Tween-80 (MIC = 0.22 μ M) than in the presence (MIC = 0.97 μ M) in the standard microplate Alamar blue assay. **Q112** displayed bactericidal activity in macrophage infections (Figure 1B). **Q112** had no observable effect on the macrophages in these experiments. **Q112** also displayed potent activity against *M. marinum* (MIC = 0.78 μ M), but was less effective against *M. smegmatis* (MIC = 25 μ M) and *M. avium* (MIC = 6.2 μ M). **Q112** displayed very weak activity

against *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (MIC = 41-82 μM). No antibacterial activity was observed against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MIC > 165 μM). These results establish **Q112** as a potent and specific antimycobacterial agent.

We also investigated the effect of **Q112** on cultured mammalian cells. **Q112** (10 μM) was largely inactive in the NCI 60 screen²³. Only three cell lines, SR (lymphoma), A498 (kidney carcinoma) and HOP-92 (non-small cell lung adenocarcinoma), were inhibited by more than 50%. Little cytotoxicity was observed in the human hepatocarcinoma cell line HepG2 ($\text{LD}_{50} \geq 19 \mu\text{M}$) or the mouse macrophage cell line J774A.1 ($\text{LD}_{50} = 50 \mu\text{M}$) under normal culture conditions. Somewhat more cytotoxicity was observed when HepG2 cells were cultured with galactose as the carbon source ($\text{LD}_{50} = 9 \mu\text{M}$), suggesting that mitochondrial toxicity may be an issue²⁴.

MtbIMPDPH2 Is Not the Q112 Target. Surprisingly, **Q112** proved to be a very modest inhibitor of *MtbIMPDPH2* ($K_{iapp} = 2.5 \mu\text{M}$). Other **Q** compounds with comparable antibacterial activity were much more potent inhibitors of *MtbIMPDPH2* activity ($K_{iapp} \leq 50 \text{ nM}$; Figure 1C)¹⁷. These observations suggested that the antibacterial activity of **Q112** might derive from an “off-target” interaction. To further assess if antibacterial activity derived from inhibition of *MtbIMPDPH2* as designed, we evaluated the effect of target depletion using the hypomorphic strain *guaB2 cKD* in which *MtbIMPDPH2* expression is suppressed by anhydrotetracycline (ATc)²⁵. Depletion hypersensitizes *guaB2 cKD* bacteria to *MtbIMPDPH2* inhibitors, including other **Q** compounds^{17, 25}. In contrast, ATc treatment had no effect on the antibacterial activity of **Q112** (Figure 1D), demonstrating that *MtbIMPDPH2* is not the **Q112** target. The structure of **Q112** does not resemble those of known tuberculosis drugs, suggesting that **Q112** may have a novel mechanism of action.

Figure 1. Antibacterial activity of Q112. **A.** Structure of **Q112**. **B.** Effect of **Q112** on macrophage infections. J774.A1 cells were infected with *Mtb* H37Rv and treated with compounds on Day 0. Colonies were enumerated in duplicate samples from at least three independent replicates of each condition after 7 days. Rif, 1 μM rifampicin; **Q112**, 2.5-20 μM, DMSO, 5 μL/mL. **C.** Correlation of antibacterial activity with inhibition of *Mtb*IMPDPH2 for **Q** compounds. Data for compounds (except **Q112**) from ¹⁷. **D.** Knockdown of *Mtb*IMPDPH2 does not hypersensitize bacteria to **Q112**. Regulated expression of *guaB2* is achieved in a TET-OFF system, as previously described ^{17,25}. Addition of anhydrotetracycline (Atc) represses expression of *guaB2*, decreasing the level of *Mtb*IMPDPH2 within the bacteria. MIC testing was carried out by broth microdilution using the AlamarBlue assay. Each point is the average of triplicates.

Table 1. Q112 antibacterial activity versus <i>Mtb</i> H37Rv.		
Media	MIC ^a (μM)	
	Day 7 ^b	Day 14 ^c
7H9/cholesterol/ dipalmitoylphosphatidylcholine/ BSA/Tyloxapol	0.78	1.5
7H9/cholesterol/BSA/Tyloxapol	0.78	0.78
7H9/Glucose/BSA/Tyloxapol	1.5	3.12
7H9/glucose/glycerol/BSA/Tween	1.5	1.5-3.12
GAST/Fe	1.5	1.5
7H9/2.5mM butyrate/pH6 /0.1mM nitrite	1.2	1.6
^a MIC, minimal inhibitory concentration. ^b Day 7, growth assessed after 7 days exposure to drug; ^c Day 14, growth assessed after 14 days exposure to drug. Media are described in Experimental Procedures.		

Preliminary Structure-Activity Relationship (SAR) for Q112. Initial exploration of the structure-activity relationship (SAR) of the benzoxazole portion of **Q112** demonstrated that repositioning of the amide nitrogen to the 6 position of the benzoxazole (**3**) had no effect on antibacterial activity and replacement of the *para*-methoxy with Cl was also tolerated (**4**). In contrast, truncation of the D-Phe side chain (**5**) and replacement of the amine with an alcohol (**6**) were deleterious. Since the D-Phe substitution distinguishes **Q112** from previously reported benzoxazole inhibitors of *Mtb*IMP2 ¹⁷, these observations prompted us to focus further SAR investigation on that region of the molecule. With the exception of D-Trp (**7**), several other hydrophobic D-amino acids could substitute for D-Phe. The D-Tyr (**8**), D-Leu (**9**) and D-Met (**10**) derivatives displayed comparable antibacterial activity to **Q112**, while the antibacterial activity of the D-Pro derivative (**11**) was

reduced by a factor of 8-30. No antibacterial activity was observed when D-Phe was substituted with D-Asp (**12**), D-Asn (**13**), D-His (**14**), D-Ser (**15**) or D-Lys (**16**). *Ortho*-F modification of the D-Phe group was tolerated (**17**), but the *ortho*-Cl substitution (**18**) increased the MIC by 3-fold. We also appended propargyl groups to either side of the molecule (**19** and **20**). Both **19** and **20** displayed equivalent antibacterial activity to that of **Q112**. These observations suggest that several avenues exist for the future medicinal chemistry optimization of **Q112**.

Table 2. Structure activity relationship of Q112 against <i>Mtb</i> H37Rv.			
Cmpd	Structure	MIC (μM) ^a	
		GAST/Fe	7H9/ADC/Tw ^b
Q112		1.56	1.56
Q111		37	25
3		1.2	1.2
4		4.7	3.13
5		12.5	12.5
6		9.4	50
7		25	25
8		1.56	1.2

9		2.3	4.7
10		4.7	6.25
11		12.5	50
12		>50	>50
13		50	>50
14		>50	>50
15		>50	>50
16		>50	>50
17		1.56	1.56
18		4.7	4.7
19		n.d.	1.2
20		n.d.	1.2
21		6.25	25

22		>50	>50
23		n.d.	≥12.5
D-Phe		n.d.	>310
^a MIC after 1 week. ^b 7H9/ADC/Tw = 7H9/glycerol/glucose/BSA/Tween.			

Q112 Derivatives Are Unstable in Plasma. We evaluated **Q112** and its most potent derivatives using *in vitro* metabolism assays to assess its suitability for testing in an animal model of *Mtb* infection (Table 3). **Q112** and **20** were rapidly metabolized in mouse liver microsomes ($\tau_{1/2}$ = 13 min and 9.1 min, respectively). We hypothesized that the methoxy group might be the liability. Consistent with this view, substitution of the methoxy with Cl (**4**) or propargyl (**19**) stabilized the compound ($\tau_{1/2}$ = 110 and \geq 30 min, respectively). **Q112** was also unstable in mouse plasma, suggesting that the amide bond might also be a liability, but this problem also appeared to be solved by the substitution of propargyl for methoxy in **19** ($\tau_{1/2}$ = 0.5 and 5 h, respectively). We further evaluated the pharmacokinetics of **19** in mice at 10 mg/kg administered orally. The value of C_{max} reached 2.1 μ M, exceeding MIC by a factor of \sim 2, with $\tau_{1/2}$ = 5 h. However, we were unable to detect free **19** in a mouse plasma protein binding experiment, indicating >99.6% is bound to plasma proteins. This result was unexpected because antibacterial activity was not diminished by the presence of albumin (compare MIC values in GAST/Fe and 7H9/ADC/Tw media in Table 2). The close agreement of the values of $\tau_{1/2}$ for plasma stability *in vivo* and *in vitro* together with the high plasma protein binding suggested that **19** was rapidly hydrolyzed upon release from plasma proteins. Further optimization to address plasma instability and improve pharmacokinetic behavior will be required before a **Q112** derivative can be tested in mice.

Table 3. <i>In vitro</i> metabolic stability, plasma protein binding and mouse pharmacokinetics (PK) of Q112 and derivatives.					
Assay		Compound			
		Q112	4	19	20
Liver microsomal stability ^a $\tau_{1/2}$ (min)		13	110	54	9.1
Plasma stability ^b $\tau_{1/2}$ (h)		~0.5	4.3	5	n.d. ^d
Plasma Protein Binding ^b (%)		n.a. ^e	n.a. ^e	>99.6	n.d. ^d
Mouse PK ^c 10 mg/kg p.o.	C _{max} (μ M)	n.d. ^d	n.d. ^d	2.1	n.d. ^d
	T _{max} (h)	n.d. ^d	n.d. ^d	1.3	n.d. ^d
	$\tau_{1/2}$ (h)	n.d. ^d	n.d. ^d	5	n.d. ^d
^a Mouse liver microsome; ^b Mouse plasma; ^c Male C57BL/6 mice (n=3), vehicle 5% DMSO/phosphate buffered saline; ^d n.d., not determined; ^e n.a., not applicable.					

Q112 Is Unlikely To Be a Prodrug. We turned our attention to the mechanism of action of **Q112**. We assessed bacterial uptake and metabolism of **Q112** using mass spectrometry. A filter carrying a mat of *Mtb* was floated over media containing **Q112** or the much less active enantiomer **Q111** (note that **Q112** was less effective when bacteria were cultured in high density on agar plates; MIC = 6 μ M). Only trace amounts of either compound were observed in the media after 24 h, indicating that the compounds were efficiently taken up by the bacteria, possibly by an active transport mechanism. Assuming that similar uptake occurs in freely replicating bacteria, the intracellular concentration of **Q112** is likely to greatly exceed the initial concentration in media, so target interactions could have much lower affinity than suggested by the MIC.

Approximately 1-2% of **Q112** was converted into a monomethylated metabolite when incubated with *Mtb*. A monomethylated metabolite was also observed when bacteria were incubated with the inactive enantiomer **Q111**. No dimethylated metabolites were detected. We synthesized two candidate **Q112** metabolites, the

methylated amine **21** and the methylated amide **22** (Table 2). **21** displayed reduced antibacterial activity (MIC = 6-25 μ M) and **22** was inactive (MIC >50 μ M). Assuming methylation does not impair uptake, it is unlikely that either compound plays a significant role in antimycobacterial activity. Although amide hydrolysis products were not observed in bacteria, we also tested the antimycobacterial activity of D-phenylalanine and **23**, neither of which were active (MIC >310 μ M and >12 μ M, respectively). These observations suggest that **Q112** is not a prodrug.

Metabolomics Suggest Q112 Inhibits Pantothenate/CoA Biosynthesis. We examined the *Mtb* metabolome after 24 h treatment with varying concentrations of **Q112** (Figure 2A and S1). Moderate increases were observed in tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle intermediates and ATP pools. These responses were complete at 1x MIC, perhaps suggesting an adaptive response. Decreases were observed in pantoate, dihydroorotate and pantetheine as well as CMP, dTMP, dTDP and dIMP. These responses were not observed in bacteria treated with the inactive isomer **Q111**, and were distinct from those associated with inhibitors of 17 well-characterized *Mtb* drug targets. Whereas *Mtb*IMPDH2 inhibitors increase IMP levels²⁰, a modest decrease in IMP was observed in **Q112** treated bacteria, confirming that **Q112** does not target *Mtb*IMPDH2. These observations further indicate that **Q112** has a novel mechanism of action.

Q112 had the largest effect on pantoate levels (~80% reduction at 10x MIC = 60 μ M), prompting closer examination of the intermediates in the essential pantothenate/CoA pathway (Figure 2B). Increases were observed in two metabolites upstream of pantoate, the immediate precursor ketopantoate (aka dehydropantoate) and 2-oxoisovalerate (aka 3-methyl-2-oxobutanoate). Few changes were observed in the downstream metabolites, with the exceptions of 4'-phosphopantothenate, which decreased by 50%, and dephospho-CoA, which increased approximately 4-fold. Similarly perplexing increases in dephospho-CoA were also observed when *panB*, *panC*, *coaBC* and *coaE* were silenced²⁶ as well as when CoaBC was inhibited by a small molecule²⁷. A small decrease was also observed in pantothenol (~20%). The enzymes responsible for the biosynthesis of pantothenol have not yet been identified. The increased ketopantoate/decreased pantoate suggested that **Q112** may inhibit ketopantoate reductase (KPR).

Figure 2. Q112 inhibits *Mtb* ketopantoate reductase (KPR). **A.** Heat map showing the metabolites most affected by **Q112**. Cells were incubated with **Q112** (6 μ M, MIC under these growth conditions) or **Q111** (10 μ M). **B.** The pantothenate/CoA biosynthetic pathway showing changes in key metabolites with **Q112** treatment. The KPR reaction is shown in red. The biosynthetic pathway for pantothenol biosynthesis (blue) has not been characterized. PanB, ketopantoate hydroxymethyl transferase; PanE, the canonical KPR; IlvC, acetohydroxy acid isomeroreductase and an alternative KPR; PanG, an alternative KPR; PanD, aspartate decarboxylase; PanC, pantothenate synthase; PanK, pantothenate kinase (aka CoaA); CoaB, phosphopantothenoilcysteine synthetase; CoaC, phosphopantothenoilcysteine decarboxylase; CoaD, phosphopantetheine adenyllyltransferase; CoaE, dephospho-CoA kinase.

The *Mtb* Genome Encodes Three KPR Candidates. Three unrelated proteins have been reported to catalyze the KPR reaction in various organisms: PanE, IlvC and PanG. PanE is considered the canonical KPR

²⁸. However, *Rv2573*, the *Mtb* gene annotated as *panE*, is not essential for *in vitro* growth in transposon mutagenesis and CRISPR interference screens, unlike other genes encoding pantothenate biosynthesis ²⁹⁻³³. Moreover, the *panE* transcript is the least abundant of any *pan* or *coa* gene transcript ²⁶, and the PanE protein is the least abundant of the Pan biosynthetic enzymes ³⁴. These observations prompted us to search for *Mtb* orthologs of IlvC and PanG.

IlvC catalyzes the ketol-acid reductoisomerase step in isoleucine/valine biosynthesis ²⁸. All IlvCs also catalyze the reduction of hydroxypyruvate, and in addition some can catalyze the reduction of ketopantoate. Loss of *ilvC* causes pantothenate auxotrophy in *Corynebacterium glutamicum*, a close relative of *Mtb* ³⁵, and IlvC is the only KPR in *Thermotoga maritima* ³⁶. These observations demonstrate that IlvC is the only protein with KPR activity in some bacteria. *Mtb*IlvC (Rv3001c) is a confirmed ketol-acid reductoisomerase ³⁷ and is essential for *in vitro* growth ²⁹⁻³². However, to our knowledge, the KPR activity of this enzyme has not been examined. We expressed and purified recombinant *Mtb*IlvC (Figure S2A). This enzyme catalyzed the reduction of hydroxypyruvate as previously observed ³⁷, but failed to catalyze the reduction of ketopantoate (activity less than 3% of hydroxypyruvate; Figure 3A). Therefore *Mtb*IlvC is unlikely to be an *Mtb* KPR.

Figure 3. Rv3603c is a PanG KPR. **A.** *Mtb*llvC does not have KPR activity. The oxidation of NADPH was monitored by change in absorbance at 340 nm. Conditions: 290 nM enzyme, 100 μM NADPH, 50 μM substrate, 4 mM MgCl_2 , 50 mM Tris/HCl, pH 8.5, 37°C. Hydroxypyruvate (Hp, red), ketopantoate (Kp, blue), no enzyme control (green), no hydroxypyruvate/ketopantoate (purple). **B.** and **C.** **Q112** inhibits *Mtb*PanG. The initial rate of NADPH consumption was monitored by the changes in absorbance at 340 nm. $[\text{E}] = 1.8 \mu\text{g/mL}$; $[\text{Q112}] = 0$, closed circles; $[\text{Q112}] = 100 \mu\text{M}$, open circles. Black lines show the fit to an uncompetitive inhibition mechanism, blue lines show the fit to a noncompetitive mechanism. **B.** Dependence of activity and **Q112** inhibition on ketopantoate concentration. Fixed $[\text{NADPH}] = 100 \mu\text{M}$. **C.** Dependence of activity and **Q112** inhibition on NADPH concentration. Fixed $[\text{ketopantoate}] = 50 \mu\text{M}$. **D.** The inhibition of *Mtb*PanG by **Q112** and derivatives. All compounds at 100 μM . $[\text{NADPH}] = 100 \mu\text{M}$, $[\text{ketopantoate}] = 20 \mu\text{M}$, $[\text{E}] = 1.8 \mu\text{g/mL}$. **E.** and **F.** **Q112** binds immobilized *Mtb*PanG as measured by biolayer interferometry. **E.** The association and dissociation of **Q112** to probe-bound *Mtb*PanG in the presence of 500 μM pantoate. Solid lines are the raw data, dashed lines are the fit to a single exponential function. **F.** The amplitudes of the binding isotherms (Panel E and Figure S6) were used to assess affinity. Lines are fits to a simple binding function.

The *panG* genes of *Francisella tularensis* and *Enterococcus faecalis* rescue pantothenate auxotrophy in KPR null strains³⁸, suggesting that *panG* encodes a protein with KPR activity. Moreover, PanG appears to be the only KPR in *F. tularensis* Schu, since deletion results in pantothenate auxotrophy³⁸. The *F. tularensis* and *E. faecalis* *panG* genes are found in operons that also contain *pan* and *coa* genes, notably *panC* (pantothenate synthase) and *panD* (aspartate decarboxylase), as well as *coaX* (type III pantothenate kinase, PANK type III). PanG is a Rossmann fold and DUF2520-domain containing protein, which further suggests that it is an oxidoreductase. However, to our knowledge, no PanG enzyme has been purified and characterized from any organism, so the redox cofactor and perhaps even the substrate of this enzyme remain to be established.

We searched the *Mtb* genome for proteins with similarity to *F. tularensis* PanG using BLAST and found Rv3603c, with 21% identity to the query sequence and 17% identity to *E. faecalis* PanG (Figure S3). The *Rv3603c* gene is part of an operon that includes *panC*, *panD* and *coaX* (*Rv3602c*, *Rv3601c*, and *Rv3600c*, respectively)³⁹, further suggesting that it has a role in pantothenate biosynthesis. Rv3603c is annotated as a conserved hypothetical protein in Mycobrowser⁴⁰, but as PanG in PATRIC⁴¹. The gene is conserved among other *Mycobacterium* species. Like other *pan* genes, *panG* is essential in transposon mutagenesis and CRISPR interference screens when bacteria are cultured on defined media with few nutrients^{30, 31, 33}, but is nonessential in rich media containing pantothenate³². Therefore Rv3603c is a strong candidate for an *Mtb* KPR.

Rv3603c Is a PanG KPR. Recombinant N-terminal His-tagged Rv3603c was expressed in *E. coli* and purified by Ni-NTA agarose affinity chromatography (Figure S2B). The purified enzyme displayed KPR activity as evidenced by the ketopantoate-dependent oxidation of NADPH. The values of K_M are $24 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$ and $2.3 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{M}$ for ketopantoate and NADPH, respectively, and the value of $V_{\text{max}} = 0.71 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mole}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (Figure 3B,C). The values of K_M are similar to those reported for the canonical PanE KPR from *E. coli* (literature values 30-120 μM and 4.0-7 μM ketopantoate and NADPH, respectively^{42, 43}). These observations establish Rv3603c as a bona fide KPR (hereafter *MtbPanG*).

PanG Is Found in Few Pathogenic Bacteria. The enzymes of the pantothenate/CoA pathway have long been considered promising targets for antimicrobial design^{44,45}. Therefore we assessed the prevalence of PanG orthologs in pathogenic bacteria using the Sequence Similarity Network (SNN) and Genome Neighborhood tools of the Enzyme Function Initiative⁴⁶. Rv3603c was used to seed a BLAST search, but none of the previously identified PanGs were retrieved. These PanGs are members of InterPro Family IPR018931, which was combined with the BLAST results to generate an SSN. All of the BLAST results were included in the family. A total 10,720 sequences were grouped into 5782 nodes, each containing sequences with 90% identity (UniRef90 sequences). No SwissProt annotations were associated with any of the sequences, further indicating that these proteins have not been functionally characterized. The network resolved into 34 clusters and 49 singletons at an alignment score of 35 (~34% identity). Only eight clusters were associated with *pan* genes with a co-occurrence ratio of at least 0.2 (Figure S4 and Table S1).

IPR018931 family members are widely distributed across the Bacterial Kingdom and is also present in Archaea. Nonetheless, relatively few pathogenic bacteria contained potential PanG orthologs. Cluster 1 (6426 sequences) contained both *MtbPanG* and *E. faecalis* PanG, as well as the *Coxiella burnetii*, *Clostridium botulinum*, *Clostridioides difficile* and *Desulfotomaculum nigrificans* orthologs previously identified³⁸. The *F. tularensis* ortholog was found in Cluster 3 (108 sequences). In addition, Cluster 1 contained potential PanGs from *E. faecium* (same node as *E. faecalis*), *Burkholderia pseudomallei* and *Burkholderia mallei*. However, only the *E. faecium* ortholog is part of a *pan* operon (Figure S5). Cluster 2, which is not associated with *pan* operons, contained orthologs from *Acinetobacter baumannii*. No potential PanG orthologs were identified in other WHO priority pathogens, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Helicobacter pylori*, *Campylobacter* spp., *Salmonellae*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Shigella*. Thus PanG inhibitors are unlikely to be broad spectrum antibiotics.

Q112 Inhibits *MtbPanG*. Q112 was a weak inhibitor of *MtbPanG* (Figure 3B,C). In general, the SAR for enzyme inhibition was similar to the SAR for antibacterial activity (Figure 3D, Table S2), with the notable exception of Q111, which displayed comparable inhibition to Q112. Unfortunately, weak inhibition and low K_m

values precluded thorough characterization of the mechanism of inhibition of *MtbPanG*. Nonetheless, **Q112** is clearly not a competitive inhibitor with respect to either ketopantoate or NADPH. The inhibition mechanism appears to be uncompetitive versus ketopantoate ($K_{ii} = 64 \pm 3 \mu\text{M}$), but we cannot distinguish uncompetitive and noncompetitive inhibition versus NADPH because we are unable to collect initial rates at concentrations lower than K_m ($K_{ii} = 113 \pm 6 \mu\text{M}$ for uncompetitive and $K_{is} = 128 \pm 4 \mu\text{M}$, $K_{ii} = 150 \pm 20 \mu\text{M}$ for noncompetitive). Importantly, the magnitude of inhibition is consistent with the metabolomics experiments, where the response to **Q112** was not saturated at $10\times \text{MIC} = 60 \mu\text{M}$.

We used biolayer interferometry (BLI) to confirm the *MtbPanG*-**Q112** interaction (Figures 3E,F and S6). This method measures changes in reflection at the surface of a fiber optic probe, which depends on both the length of the optical path and spectral properties. *MtbPanG* was immobilized to the fiber optic probe via the 6xHis-tag, and the probe was submerged in varying fixed concentrations of **Q112**. The binding isotherms were multi-phasic, so the amplitude of the equilibrium response was used to calculate binding affinity⁴⁷, yielding $K_d \gg 100 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure 3F). The weak association of **Q112** with *MtbPanG* is consistent with the observation that **Q112** is an uncompetitive inhibitor and therefore binds after substrates. Therefore we also assessed binding in the presence of the products NADP^+ and pantoate. The addition of NADP^+ had no effect on **Q112** binding (Figure 3E and S6). However, single exponential binding was observed in the presence of pantoate (Figure 3E), yielding $k_{on} = 2 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $k_{off} = 0.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $K_d = 250 \mu\text{M}$. These values were in good agreement with the value of K_d determined from the response at 150 s (R_{150}) ($K_d = 240 \mu\text{M}$; Figure 3F). These observations suggest that **Q112** binds preferentially to the *Mtb*-pantoate complex.

Q112 Has an Additional Target(s). Pantothenate rescues gene disruptions in the pantothenate/CoA pathway in *Mtb*, including loss of function of *panB*, *panC*, *panD*, *coaBC* and *coaE*^{26, 32, 48, 49}. However, pantothenate failed to protect bacteria from **Q112** (Table S3). Pantoate and pantolactone, which rescue the loss of KPR activity in other bacteria³⁸, also failed to protect *Mtb* against **Q112**. These observations suggest that although **Q112** disrupts the pantothenate/CoA pathway, another target is responsible for antibacterial activity.

Q112-Resistant Strains Display Widespread Changes in Antibiotic Susceptibility. To further investigate the mechanism of action of **Q112**, we isolated spontaneously resistant strains by selecting single colonies on solid medium containing **Q112** (5x MIC and 10x MIC). Seven modestly resistant clones were obtained (MIC = 12.5 μ M versus 3.1 μ M for wild-type, Table 4) with a frequency of resistance of $\sim 10^{-8}$. All of the **Q112**-resistant clones displayed severe growth defects on both solid and liquid media.

We examined the antibiotic susceptibility of five **Q112**-resistant strains, A3, A6, B1, B2 and B3, to gain further insights into the effects of the mutations (the remaining two strains did not grow sufficiently well to permit further investigation) (Table 4). Curiously, while wild-type bacteria are resistant to ampicillin due to the action of β -lactamase BlaC (MIC > 50 μ M), all five **Q112**-resistant strains were susceptible, with values of MIC decreasing by more than a factor of 16 (MIC = 1.6 - 3.1 μ M) (Table 4). The ampicillin susceptibility of the **Q112**-resistant strains was similar to that of the wild-type strain in the presence of the β -lactamase inhibitor clavulanate (MIC = 2.3 μ M). All five strains were also hypersensitive to rifampicin (factors of 3-6) and vancomycin (factors of 4-5), but resistant to delamanid (MIC increased 3-12-fold). None of the strains displayed altered susceptibility (MIC changed by more than a factor of 3) to imipenem, imipenem plus clavulanate, meropenem, meropenem plus clavulanate, cycloserine, clofazimine, moxifloxacin, linezolid, bedaquiline, isoniazid, ethionamide, ethambutol and p-aminosalicylic acid, with the exception of B3, which was resistant to imipenem (16-fold), imipenem plus clavulanate (8-fold) and clofazimine (4-fold). Given the disparate mechanisms of action of delamanid (mycolic acid biosynthesis inhibitor), imipenem (cell wall biosynthesis inhibitor) and clofazimine (ATP biosynthesis inhibitor), it seems unlikely that resistance derives from alteration of a target shared with **Q112**. The poor fitness of the **Q112**-resistant strains and their hypersensitivity to rifampicin suggest that cross-resistance is unlikely to be an issue in the clinic.

Table 4. Antibiotic susceptibility of Q112-resistant strains.

Antibiotic	MIC (μM) ^a						MOA
	WT	A3 <i>tatB</i>	A6 <i>tatB</i>	B1 <i>tatC</i>	B2 <i>tatC</i>	B3 <i>tatA</i>	
Q112	3.13	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	unknown
Ampicillin	>50	3.1	3.1	1.6	2.3	3.1	cell wall biosynthesis
Ampicillin + clavulanate	2.3	0.39	0.78	0.2	0.39	0.78	cell wall biosynthesis
Meropenem	1.2	0.39- 0.6	0.78	0.39- 0.6	0.39	0.78	cell wall biosynthesis
Meropenem + clavulanate	0.39	0.2	0.2	0.15	0.2	0.39	cell wall biosynthesis
Imipenem	0.39	0.6	0.78	0.39	0.39	6.2	cell wall biosynthesis
Imipenem + clavulanate	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.15	1.6	cell wall biosynthesis
Rifampicin	0.012	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.0028	RNA polymerase
Streptomycin	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46	protein synthesis
Capreomycin	0.78	0.78	1.2	0.78	1.2	0.78	protein synthesis
Linezolid	0.78	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	1.56	protein synthesis
Moxifloxacin	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.16	0.12	DNA gyrase, topoisomerase
Bedaquiline	0.31	0.46	0.63	0.46	0.46	0.46	ATP synthesis
Clofazimine	0.16	0.16	0.24	0.12	0.24	0.63	ATP synthesis
Delamanid	0.0031	0.038	0.0092	0.019	0.019	0.0092	mycolic acid biosynthesis
Isoniazid	0.31	0.12	0.078	0.16	0.12	0.16	mycolic acid biosynthesis
Ethionamide	0.3	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	mycolic acid biosynthesis
Ethambutol	1.6	3.1	2.4	2.4	3.12	3.1	arabinogalactan biosynthesis
p-Aminosalicylic acid	0.3	0.39	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.6	folic acid biosynthesis and

							cell wall biosynthesis
D-Cycloserine	4.7	12	9.4	9.4	9.4	12	cell wall biosynthesis
Vancomycin	5	1.2	1.2	0.92	0.92	1.2	cell wall biosynthesis
^a MICs for Q112 -resistant strains were determined after two weeks. MOA, mechanism of action. The gene mutated in each strain is listed below the strain designation.							

Q112-Resistant Strains Contain Loss of Function Mutations in TatABC. We sequenced the genomes of the **Q112**-resistant strains to further investigate the mechanism of resistance. Four strains contained mutations in *fadD26*, a gene involved in phthiocerol dimycocerosate (PDIM) biosynthesis. Such mutations are known to cause a fitness advantage in culture and are frequently encountered in laboratory strains⁵⁰. Therefore these mutations were unlikely to cause **Q112** resistance.

All seven strains contained distinct mutations in one of the three subunits of the twin arginine translocase (TatABC)⁵¹. TatABC is responsible for the secretion of folded proteins containing Arg-Arg motif signal peptides. To the best of our knowledge, these are the first examples of resistance deriving from mutations of TatABC, further underscoring the novel mechanism of action of **Q112**. Four strains contained mutations in *tatC* (Tables S4). This subunit is the core of the translocase responsible for signal peptide and client binding⁵¹. Strains A2 and A5 contained missense mutations that substitute Pro for Leu at positions 217 and 125, respectively⁵¹. These residues are part of the concave surface that is believed to bind client proteins, and both residues are adjacent to sites of inactivating mutations (Figure 4)⁵². PROVEAN analysis indicates that these substitutions are likely to be deleterious (scores -5.7 and -6.2 for L125P and L217P, respectively⁵³). Strain B1 contained a nonsense mutation that truncated TatC at Tyr123, removing 103 residues from the C-terminus. Strain B2 contained a deletion that changed the reading frame at position 195, resulting in a 206 residue protein. Therefore, it seems likely that all the TatC mutations may have loss of function phenotypes. Two strains contained mutations in *tatB* that are also likely to be inactivating. Strain A2 contained an insertion that changes the reading frame at residue 10 and strain A6 contained a missense mutation in the start codon, substituting Met1 with Ala. Lastly, strain B3 contained a single nucleotide deletion that changes the TatA reading frame at residue 58 such that a 397 residue fusion protein is created with TatC. Similar *E. coli* TatB-C

fusion proteins are inactive⁵⁴. These observations suggest that **Q112** resistance may derive from loss of function of TatABC in all seven strains.

TatABC is involved in the secretion of a wide variety of proteins, including β -lactamases (BlaC), nutrient transporters, cell wall biosynthesis enzymes and electron transport proteins in *Mtb* and related bacteria⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. Not surprisingly, growth phenotypes were observed in knockout and knockdown experiments^{29-31, 33, 55}. Therefore loss of TatABC function explains the poor growth phenotype of the **Q112**-resistant strains. Loss of TatABC would impair the secretion of substrate proteins, with widespread effects on drug permeability. For example, the β -lactamase BlaC is a well characterized TatABC substrate⁵⁶, so loss of TatABC can account for ampicillin susceptibility. Predicted TatABC clients include three efflux pumps associated with antibiotic uptake, Rv0194, Rv0849 and Rv3239c⁵⁸. Thus loss of TatABC function can explain the changes in antibiotic susceptibility associated with **Q112** resistance.

Mtb	VRAAGLLKRLNPNRRSRVNPDMATMSLV ⁵⁴ DHLTELRLRLISLAA ⁵⁴ ILVTTIFGFVWYSHSI	60
Aqae	-----MPLTEHLRELRVRLIISIIAFLIGSGIAF-YFAKYV	35
Eco	-----MSVEDTQPL ⁵² ITHLIELRRLNLCIIIVIVIFLCLV-YFANDI	41
Mtb	FGLDSLGEWLRHPYCALPQSARADISADGECRLLATAPFDQFMLRLKVGMAAGIVLACPV	120
Aqae	FEILK-----EPILK-----SYPEVE-LITLSPTEPLFILLKISLAVGFIIASPV	79
Eco	YHLVS-----APLIK-----QLRQGSTMIATDVASPEFTPIKLT ⁵⁴ FMVSLILSAPV	86
Mtb	WFYQLWAFITPGLYQRRERFAVAFVIPA ⁵⁴ AVLFVAGAVL ⁵⁴ AYLV-LSKALG ⁵⁴ LLTVGSDVQV	179
Aqae	I ⁵⁴ LYQFWR ⁵⁴ FIEPALYSHEKRAFIP ⁵⁴ LLGSIL ⁵⁴ LFMLGALFAYFIVLPLAL ⁵⁴ KFLLGLGFTQLL	139
Eco	I ⁵⁴ LYQVNAFIAPALYKHERRLVV ⁵⁴ PLLVSSLL ⁵⁴ FYIGMAFAYFVVF ⁵⁴ PLAFGLANTAPEGVQ	146
Mtb	T--ALSGDRYFG ⁵⁴ FLNLLVVF ⁵⁴ GVSE ⁵⁴ FEF ⁵⁴ LLIVMLNLAGLTYERL ⁵⁴ KS ⁵⁴ WRRGLIFAMFVFA	237
Aqae	ATPYLSVDMYISFV ⁵⁴ LKLVVAF ⁵⁴ GI ⁵⁴ AFEM ⁵⁴ PIVLYVLQKAGVITPEQLASFRKYFIVIAFVIG	199
Eco	VS--TDIASYLSFV ⁵⁴ MA ⁵⁴ LFMA ⁵⁴ FGVSE ⁵⁴ VEV ⁵⁴ VAIVLLCWMGITSPEDLRK ⁵⁴ KRPV ⁵⁴ LVGAFVVG	204
Mtb	AI ⁵⁴ FTPGSD ⁵⁴ PF ⁵⁴ SMTALGAALTV ⁵⁴ LLELAIQIARV ⁵⁴ HDK ⁵⁴ RRKAKREAAIPDDEASVIDPPSPVPA	297
Aqae	AI ⁵⁴ IA-P-DVSTQVLM ⁵⁴ AIPL ⁵⁴ LLLYEISIFL ⁵⁴ GK ⁵⁴ LATR ⁵⁴ KKKEIQKA-PGSENLYFQ-----	249
Eco	MLLTPP-DVFS ⁵⁴ Q ⁵⁴ LLAIPMYCL ⁵⁴ FEIGVFFSRFYV ⁵⁴ GKGRNREEE-NDAAEASEKTEE----	258
Mtb	PSVIGSHDDVT	308
Aqae	-----	249
Eco	-----	258

Figure 4. TatC mutations. A. Alignment of TatC from *Mtb*, *E. coli* (*Eco*) and *Aquifex aeolicus* (*Aqae*).

Conserved residues are highlighted in yellow, sites of inactivating mutations on *E. coli* TatC are shown in cyan^{52, 54, 59} and sites of missense mutations in **Q112**-resistant strains are shown in magenta. B. The positions of *Mtb* TatC mutations L125P and L217P (magenta) are mapped onto the structure of *A. aeolicus* TatC (PDB id 4B4A). Positions of previously identified inactivating mutations are shown in cyan. The dotted ellipse denotes the signal peptide binding region.

DISCUSSION

New antibiotics with novel mechanisms of action are needed to treat both drug sensitive and drug resistant tuberculosis. Here, we report a D-phenylalanine-benzoxazole derivative **Q112** with potent antimycobacterial activity under all culture conditions examined, with bactericidal activity in macrophage infections. **Q112** derivatives are unstable in plasma, suggesting that the amide bond is a liability; many stable amide bioisosteres are available to address this issue⁶⁰ and initial SAR studies suggest multiple avenues are available for further medicinal chemistry optimization to improve potency and pharmacokinetic properties.

Although originally designed as an *Mtb* IMPDH2 inhibitor, the antibacterial activity of **Q112** derives from a novel mechanism. Metabolomic experiments suggested that **Q112** inhibits the KPR reaction in the essential pantothenate/CoA pathway. CoA is required for the synthesis of fatty acids, including the mycolic acids that make up the mycobacterial cell wall, and pantothenate/CoA biosynthesis has long been considered a promising source of new targets for *Mtb* and other pathogens^{44, 45}. Pantothenate biosynthesis enzymes are not present in mammals and the coenzyme A biosynthesis enzymes are highly diverged, presenting many opportunities for the design of selective inhibitors^{45, 61}. The pathway is essential in *Mtb* in transposon in the absence of pantothenate²⁹⁻³², an *Mtb* Δ *panCD* strain is severely attenuated in mice⁴⁸, and *panB*, *panD*, *panC*, *coaBC* and *coaE* are essential and vulnerable as demonstrated by gene silencing^{26, 33, 62}. Moreover, the antibacterial activity of the frontline drug pyrazinamide appears to derive at least in part from the degradation of PanD (aspartate decarboxylase)⁶³, demonstrating the clinical utility of disrupting this pathway. The potential of this pathway is also illustrated by the *in vivo* antibacterial activity of a 4'-phosphopanthetheinyl transferase inhibitor⁶⁴. Yet despite much attention, efforts to exploit this pathway have been largely unsuccessful and few inhibitors of these enzymes have been reported^{27, 45, 65, 66}.

Surprisingly given the above, the gene annotated as the canonical *Mtb* KPR PanE is nonessential²⁹⁻³¹. This discrepancy prompted us to search for alternative KPRs. We found *Rv3603c*, a conserved and essential gene among *Mycobacteria*, encodes *Mtb*PanG. To our knowledge, *Mtb*PanG is the first PanG KPR to be purified and characterized. Given the low expression of PanE^{26, 34}, we cautiously suggest that *Mtb*PanG may

be responsible for the majority of ketopantoate reduction in *Mtb*. **Q112** is a modest inhibitor of recombinant *Mtb*PanG, explaining the accumulation of ketopantoate and depletion of downstream metabolites observed with **Q112** treatment. A recent assessment of target vulnerability in *Mtb* indicates that *Mtb*PanG is a good candidate target comparable to PanC and PanD (vulnerability index = -4.267, -3.926 and -4.065, respectively)³³.

The essentiality of KPR in other pathogenic bacteria is uncertain given the unpredictable redundancy of PanE, IlvC and PanG. Similar redundancy appears in other steps in the pantothenate/CoA pathway. Like KPRs, three different pantothenate kinases (PANK types I, II and III) have been characterized in various organisms⁴⁴. *Mtb* appears to contain orthologs for both type I (encoded by *coaA*) and type III (*Rv3600c/coaX*)⁴⁹. Curiously, although the putative *coaX* is part of the same operon as *Rv3603c*, it has not been possible to verify that this enzyme has PanK activity⁴⁹ and this gene is not essential. In contrast, type I PANK is essential in both transposon screens and targeted gene knockout studies, although almost complete inhibition is required to deplete the coenzyme A pools sufficiently for antibacterial activity^{26, 67}. It is tempting to speculate that the invulnerability of the type I PANK may be due in part to the presence of *coaX*. Unappreciated redundancy may occur in other steps of the pantothenate/CoA pathway. Thus the allure of the pantothenate/CoA pathway for antibiotic discovery should be tempered by the unpredictable repertoire of enzymes catalyzing these reactions.

Our experiments also demonstrate that significant gaps remain in our understanding of the pathways governing pantothenate/CoA biosynthesis. Perplexing accumulation/depletion patterns observed in our experiments and those of Evans suggest additional regulatory mechanisms control flux through the pantothenate/CoA pathway^{26, 27}. As noted by others^{27, 68}, the failure to observe depletion of CoA may derive from the recycling of phosphopantetheine from acyl carrier proteins. Moreover, the pathways responsible for at least one pantothenate/CoA metabolite, pantothenol, have yet to be described in any organism. Interestingly, Lau and colleagues have shown that *Mtb* secretes pantothenol (aka dexpanthenol) into the culture medium⁶⁹, while others report that pantothenol has antibacterial attributed to the inhibition of CoaBC by its phosphorylated metabolite in *Mtb*⁷⁰.

The inhibition *MtbPanG* accounts for the perturbation of the pantothenate/CoA pathway, but does not explain the antibacterial activity of **Q112**. Pantothenate fails to protect bacteria against **Q112**, although it rescues other forms of pantothenate auxotrophy^{26, 32, 48, 49}. Distinct differences are also observed in the metabolomic responses of **Q112** treatment and *pan/coa* gene silencing. **Q112** causes an *increase* in TCA cycle intermediates, while knockdown of *panB*, *panC*, *coaBC* or *coaE* all produced a *depletion* of these metabolites²⁶. The metabolomic response to **Q112** is unlike that of other anti-TB agents, which underscores its unique mechanism but frustrates target identification since rarely do enzyme inhibitors elicit simple patterns of substrate accumulation/product depletion. Indeed, ketopantoate/pantoate was the only substrate accumulation/product depletion pair identified in metabolomic experiments. Resistant strains have also failed to clarify the mechanism of action of **Q112**. Loss of function mutations in the protein translocase TatABC provide modest resistance to **Q112**, accompanied by substantial fitness defects. TatABC mutants have not been previously associated with antibiotic resistance. TatABC clients include enzymes involved in cell wall biosynthesis, nutrient uptake, efflux and electron transport^{55-57, 71, 72}, accounting for poor fitness. Uptake defects can also account for **Q112**-resistance.

While we have been unable to fully elucidate the mechanism of action of **Q112**, our experiments clearly indicate that **Q112** engages *MtbPanG* and at least one additional target. Multi-target antibiotics are relatively "resistance-resistant"⁵, which has spurred a growing interest in multi-target drug design for tuberculosis⁷⁻¹⁵. One such compound, SQ109, is currently in clinical trials⁷. In addition to *MtbPanG* and *MtbIMPDH2*, benzoxazole inhibitors have been reported for *MtbGroEL/ES* and protein tyrosine phosphatase B¹³, suggesting that this scaffold is particularly well suited for multi-target antibiotic development. Efforts are underway to identify additional **Q112** targets to facilitate further development of this scaffold.

Conclusions. Here we report compound **Q112** with potent antibacterial activity against *Mtb* and a unique mechanism of action. **Q112** perturbs the essential pantothenate/coenzyme A biosynthesis pathway by inhibiting a previously unrecognized ketopantoate reductase. **Q112** also has another as yet undefined target.

Bacteria are less prone to develop resistance to multi-target drugs, which makes **Q112** an intriguing scaffold for further development.

METHODS

Materials. NADPH was purchased from Chem-Impex (Wood Dale, IL). Ketopantoic acid, pantoic acid, hydroxypyruvate, pantolactone, pantothenate, Tris and common chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St, Louis, MO). The synthesis of the **Q112** derivatives is described in the Supporting Information.

Antibacterial assays. *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv was obtained from laboratory stocks. MICs were determined as previously described¹⁷. Methods are described in the Supporting Information.

Metabolite Analysis. Bacteria-laden nitrocellulose filter were incubated with varying concentrations of **Q112** in a swimming pool set up as previously described.⁷³ More detailed methods can be found in the Supporting Information.

Recombinant Enzyme Purification. *Mtb*IMP2 was purified as previously described^{16,17}. C-terminally His-tagged variants of *Mtb*IlvC (UniProt: P9WKJ7) and *Mtb*PanG (UniProt: O06279) were produced from codon-optimized genes using pET28a(+) expression vectors (GenScript, Piscataway, NJ). The sequences are available in Supporting Table S4. *Mtb*IlvC was expressed in *E. coli* BL21(DE3) and *Mtb*PanG was expressed in *E. coli* BL21(DE3). Both enzymes were purified using Ni-NTA-agarose resin.

Enzyme Assays. IMPDH activity was determined by measuring the production of NADH as previously described^{16,17}. IlvC activity was determined by measuring the consumption of NADPH by absorbance at 340 nm³⁷. Assays were typically performed in 4 mM MgCl₂, 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.5, 100 μM NADPH, 50-100 μM hydroxypyruvate at 37°C. KPR activity was determined by measuring the consumption of NADPH by absorbance at 340 nm⁴². Assays were typically performed in 100 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 100 μM NADPH, 5-250 μM ketopantoic acid at 25°C.

Real time binding data was measured using a ForteBio BLItz instrument in combination with Octet® NTA Biosensors following procedures recommended by the manufacturer. Experiments were performed in phosphate buffered saline, pH 7.4, 0.002% Tween-20, 0.1 mg/ml bovine serum albumin and 2% DMSO at room temperature. C-terminally His-tagged *MtbPanG* (50 µg/mL) was immobilized onto the NTA biosensor. The probe was equilibrated assay buffer and transferred to a reservoir containing varying concentrations of **Q112** as the analyte. After the association reaction was complete, the probe was transferred to assay buffer and the dissociation reaction was monitored. Association and dissociation data were fit to single exponential models using Prism-GraphPad.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information: The Supporting Information is available free of charge at

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsinfecdis.xxx>.

- Figure S1. **Q112** induced changes in the *Mtb* metabolome.
- Figure S2. Purification of *Mtb* IlvC and Rv3603c (PanG).
- Figure S3. Alignment of Rv3603c and PanGs from *Francisella tularensis* and *Enterococcus faecalis*.
- Figure S4. Sequence similarity network for InterPro Family IPR018931.
- Figure S5. Genome neighborhoods for putative PanGs from pathogenic bacteria.
- Figure S6. Biolayer interferometry analysis of the interaction of Q112 with immobilized *MtbPanG*.
- Table S1. PanG clusters with *pan* gene neighbors.
- Table S2. Inhibition of Rv3603c by **Q112** and derivatives.
- Table S3. Pantothenate and related metabolites have no effect on the antibacterial activity of **Q112**.
- Table S4. Whole genome sequencing results of **Q112**-resistant strains.
- Table S5. Sequences of recombinant enzymes.
- Table S6. Compound naming convention.

- Methods: Bacterial Strains and Culture Conditions, MIC Determinations, Efficacy in Macrophage Infections, *Mtb*IMPDH2 Downregulation, Isolation of Q112-Resistant Bacteria, *In Vitro* Drug Metabolism and Plasma Protein Binding, Mouse Pharmacokinetics, Metabolite Analysis, Recombinant Enzyme Purification.
- Compound Synthesis and Characterization.

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ABBREVIATIONS USED

ATc, anhydrotetracycline; CoaB, phosphopantothencysteine synthetase; CoaC, phosphopantothencysteine decarboxylase; CoaD, Phosphopantetheine adenylyltransferase; CoaE, dephospho-CoA kinase; DMSO, dimethylsulfoxide; IlvC, acetohydroxy acid isomeroreductase; IMPDH, 5'-inosine monophosphate dehydrogenase; KPR, ketopantoate reductase; MIC, minimal inhibitory concentration; *Mtb*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*; PBS, phosphate buffered saline; PanB, ketopantoate hydroxymethyl transferase; PanC, pantothenate synthase; PanD, aspartate decarboxylase; PanE, the canonical KPR; PanG, an alternative KPR; PANK, pantothenate kinase (aka CoaA); PK, pharmacokinetics; SAR, structure activity relationship; Tat, twin arginine translocase.

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A D-Phenylalanine-Benzoxazole Derivative Reveals the Role of the Essential Enzyme Rv3603c in the Pantothenate Biosynthetic Pathway of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

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New antibiotics are urgently needed to treat tuberculosis. **Q112** displays potent antibacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*). We find that **Q112** inhibits Rv3603c, an essential enzyme of previously unknown function now identified as PanG. This enzyme catalyzes conversion of ketopantoate to pantoate, a key step in the biosynthesis of CoA. However, PanG inhibition cannot account for antibacterial activity and additional **Q112** targets remain to be identified.